

Position statement: BonaRes Repository as trusted repository in accordance with Horizon Europe criteria

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Trusted repositories are defined by Horizon Europe as either

- Certified repositories (e.g., CoreTrustSeal, nestor Seal DIN31644, ISO16363) or disciplinary and domain repositories commonly used and endorsed by the research communities. Such repositories should be recognized internationally.
- General-purpose repositories or institutional repositories that present the essential characteristics of trusted repositories.

The BonaRes Repository is currently in the process of obtaining [CoreTrustSeal certification](#). Reviewer feedback is being addressed, and the certification is anticipated to be completed by 2024. Additionally, the BonaRes Repository is recognized as an open access repository in both the 'DFG RIsources' (https://risources.dfg.de/detail/RI_00508_en.html) and 'OpenDOAR' (<https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/id/repository/10039>) directories. The BonaRes Repository is an internationally recognized, domain specific repository for agricultural research data, funded and perpetuated at the institutional level.

Requirements and characteristics of a trusted repository and realization in the BonaRes Repository (BR)

- Trusted repositories display specific characteristics of organizational, technical and procedural quality such as services, mechanisms and/or provisions that are intended to secure the integrity and authenticity of their contents, thus facilitating their use and reuse in the short- and long-term.
 - BR makes use of technical measures such as digital signatures (e.g., the creation of MD5 hashes during data ingestion) and time stamps to ensure (data) integrity and authenticity as well as protection against (data) falsification.
- Trusted repositories have specific provisions in place and offer explicit information online about their policies, which define their services (e.g. acquisition, access, security of content, long-term sustainability of service including funding etc.).
 - A continuously adapted online help ([FAIRagro Helpdesk](#)) and personal data stewards support (support-data@bonares.de) is provided, as well as guidelines (<https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-mvkn-a4mb>) on publishing research data. Explicit information about services is published in the BonaRes Data Policy (<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.20387/BonaRes-RYCV-30RK>).
- Provide broad, equitable and ideally open access to content free at the point of use, as appropriate, and respect applicable legal and ethical limitations.
 - Published resources, including data and metadata, are openly accessible in line with the open access paradigm. In cases where a temporary embargo is in place, metadata remains freely available while access to the data is restricted. During this period, contact to the author to request data access is ensured.
- They assign persistent unique identifiers to contents (e.g. DOIs, handles, etc.), such that the contents (publications, data and other research outputs) are unequivocally referenced and thus citable.

- Once published in BR, each dataset is assigned to a DOI (prefixes: <https://doi.org/10.20387> and <https://doi.org/10.4228>). These DOIs are registered with DataCite through the TIB (German National Library of Science and Technology).
- They ensure that contents are accompanied by metadata sufficiently detailed and of high quality to enable discovery, reuse and citation and contain information about provenance and licensing; metadata are machine-actionable and standardized (e.g. Dublin Core, Data Cite etc.) preferably using common non-proprietary formats and following the standards of the respective community the repository serves, where applicable.
 - Data is described by descriptive and administrative metadata (following DataCite and INSPIRE standards), including licensing details such as ‘Creative Commons CC-BY’ licenses. The metadata is human-readable within the repository and can be downloaded as a PDF. Additionally, the metadata is machine-actionable, available in XML format (ISO 19139:2007) and as JSON in schema.org format via API access.
- Facilitate mid-and long-term preservation of the deposited material.
 - Long-term storage is ensured for a minimum of ten years using ZALF’s own infrastructure resources. For archiving beyond ten years, including bit-stream-preservation, migration, and metadata curation, the repository collaborates with external partners to ensure sustained preservation.
- They have mechanisms or provisions for expert curation and quality assurance for the accuracy and integrity of datasets and metadata, as well as procedures to liaise with depositors where issues are detected.
 - Metadata are reviewed by data stewards before publication and during ingestion. If any issues are identified, established procedures ensure direct communication with the authors. Authors must have a valid user account in the repository, including a valid email address. During submission, a ticket is generated containing the author’s and institution’s contact information. This is used for all further communication between author and data stewards (editorial team) until the data are published.
- They meet generally accepted international and national criteria for security to prevent unauthorized access and release of content and have different levels of security depending on the sensitivity of the data being deposited to maintain privacy and confidentiality.
 - Data publication is carried out by the data stewards, not by the authors.
 - Only authorized data stewards can change data and metadata once published; each alteration is documented in the lineage element of the metadata and thus transparent.
 - Sensitive research data is sufficiently anonymized before publication.
 - All sensitive personal data is managed according to the [GDPR](#) rules.

Conclusion

From the standpoint of the ZALF Research Data Management, researchers applying for funding in the Horizon Europe program should be able to use the BonaRes Repository for the publication of their research data. The BonaRes Repository is expected to receive trusted repository certification by the end of 2024, at latest by 2025.

Repository requirements as referenced from European Commission (2021). EU Grants: AGA — Annotated Model Grant Agreement: V1.0 1.5.2025. EU Programmes 2021-2027. HE. Horizon Europe and Euratom. https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf (see p. 376ff).